

Technical report

Unblocking the Datapath: Phase-Aware Reshaping of HPC Workloads to Mitigate I/O Contention

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This technical report describes some technical concepts introduced in Section 3 in the main paper in the paper "Unblocking the Datapath: Phase-Aware Reshaping of HPC Workloads to Mitigate I/O Contention".

Certain concepts require extensive description and detailed technical context for a complete understanding. Due to this, we have developed this supplementary resource. It provides in-depth explanations for the main components used in the main work, and additional plots to reflect the phases of our proposal.

1 Petri Net and its Extensions

A Petri Net (PN) is a graphical and mathematical modeling tool composed of two primary elements: (i) places (graphically depicted as circles), which represent the states or conditions of the system, and (ii) transitions (graphically depicted as boxes), which represent events or actions that can occur. Places can hold tokens (shown as black dots), which signify the presence of certain system entities or resources. Arcs connect places to transitions (or vice versa) and define how tokens move when an event occurs. Each arc has multiplicity, indicating how many tokens are consumed from input places or produced into output places when a transition fires. If this value is one, it is usually omitted for simplicity. To capture intricate or structured systems more effectively, Extended Stochastic Symmetric Nets (ESSNs)[2,3], and Generally Distributed Extended Stochastic Petri Nets (GDESPNs) expand the foundational PN model. These enhancements permit a more generalized and intricate depiction of the system under study. Specifically, it is possible to represent systems in a more compact and expressive way by distinguishing between diverse token types without necessitating replication of large parts of the net, by introducing labels called colors to tokens, places, and transitions. Within an ESSN, each place is associated with a color domain

(comprising all possible token types) represented by $cd(p)$. These domains are defined as Cartesian products of color classes, $\mathcal{C} = C_1, \dots, C_n$, which are finite, disjoint sets. Optionally, color classes can be divided into static subclasses to reflect fixed groupings. Likewise, transitions are associated with typed variables, which are used in arc expressions and are typed according to these color classes. A transition becomes enabled (i.e., ready to fire) if all its input places contain enough tokens to satisfy the multiplicity constraints defined by the incoming arcs. When a transition fires, it removes the required number of tokens from its input places and adds new tokens to its output places, following the rules specified by the output arcs.

As an example, the ESSN model in Figure 1 (discussed in detail in the next section) includes nine places, eight transitions, and a single color class called *Application*. Every place shares the same color domain based on this class, and all arcs use the same typed variable, $\langle a \rangle$. For instance, the transition *IO_start* can only fire if both *IOQueue* and *Servers* have at least one token. If so, it consumes one token from each and produces tokens in the connected output places. Each transition is further associated with a firing rate, which is the parameter of an exponential distribution describing the delay before the transition occurs. This stochastic timing enables the automatic construction of a Continuous Time Markov Chain (CTMC) [1], which can be analyzed to evaluate system performance.

In general, the GDESPN formalism allows for transitions to follow arbitrary time distributions, not just exponential ones. These are known as general transitions and are depicted as black boxes. In the model presented in this paper, only the *InitApp* transition uses a non-exponential timing: it follows a Dirac delta distribution, representing a deterministic delay where the event occurs at an exact time. Despite this deviation, the resulting stochastic model remains Markovian. For simplicity, we refer to the model as an ESSN throughout the paper, even though it includes one general transition.

2 The Markovian Model

We define an ESSN model, illustrated in Figure 1, to simulate the behavior of an HPC system where multiple applications can run concurrently. To achieve this, we introduce a color class *Application* that comprises a variable number of subclasses, each representing a distinct application to be simulated within the system. As a result, each application is uniquely identified by a subclass within the color class *Application*. A token with color tuple $\langle a \rangle$ represents an instance of application $a \in App_1$. The model consists of nine places and eight transitions, which capture the three states (I/O, MPI, and non-I/O/MPI computations) that an application can traverse, as well as concurrent I/O computations.

Specifically, an application $\langle a \rangle$ can occupy a specific state represented by the places *IO*, *MPI*, and *OTHER*. For example, all applications start at the *Applications* place and, through the general transition *InitApp* governed by a δ distribution, they initiate execution beginning with I/O in the *IOQueue* place.

Fig. 1: ESSN representation of the HPC machine model.

Notably, each application $\langle a \rangle$ is assigned a starting time t_0^a , which determines when it enters the system; specifically, the application becomes active only when the simulation time reaches t_0^a . Importantly, choosing I/O as the initial state does not impose strong assumptions, as an analysis of the model’s initial marking revealed that the starting state has a negligible impact on the simulations. In *IOQueue*, an application $\langle a \rangle$ waits for service from the first available server; here, the *Servers* place represents the number of servers managing I/O in the *IOQueue*. Upon transition to the I/O state, i.e., the token representing the application $\langle a \rangle$ is added to the place *IO* through the transition *IO_start*, the next state is determined by the transitions *IO_to_MPI* or *IO_to_OTHER*. Depending on which transition occurs, the application will either start MPI or computation, respectively, by moving the token into the corresponding place, either *MPI* or *OTHER*. Then, the other part of the ESSN works in the same manner. The places *MPI_hits*, *IO_hits*, and *OTHER_hits* serve as cumulative counters, tracking how many times MPI, I/O, and other computations are called, respectively.

3 Data Analysis and Machine Model Calibration

As previously mentioned in Section 5 in the main paper, this section provides a more detailed description of our proposed workflow, which consists of three key

steps: a) processing the monitoring data, b) detecting the distinct phases, and c) calibrating the machine model using the insights gained from these phases.

Data Processing The monitoring infrastructure gathers a vast amount of performance metrics related to the application (captured in a trace). However, since our model (Section 2) simplifies the system into three states - I/O, MPI, and other computations (encompassing GPU and CPU) - we need to filter the numerous metrics from this trace to select only those that provide valuable insights for calibrating the model. In this study, we concentrate on I/O-related aspects, so our system filters out all irrelevant information and focuses exclusively on I/O-related metrics while disregarding computation-related ones, collectively referred to as *OTHER*. Furthermore, we have not addressed the case of asynchronous I/O, which is more complex to track using a single timeline. In this context, we define \mathcal{M} as the set of metric names that provide valuable information: (1) the total time spent in MPI operations; (2) the total number of MPI calls; (3-4) the total counts of `read` and `write` operations, respectively; and (5-6) the total times spent on `read` and `write` operations. Note that the total number of I/O calls is approximately equal to the sum of `read` and `write` operations.

Phase Detection involves analyzing the application traces generated during data processing to identify recurring patterns within them. Application traces are characterized by periodic repetitions of similar patterns and abrupt changes in computations, allowing us to associate a set of parameters with each distinct pattern and change in the temporal trace. For our use cases, we detected three phases for EpiGraph and two for malleable benchmarks. Figure 2 shows clustered phases identified by *FTIO+Kmeans* for both applications across different numbers of processes. We analyzed at least five independent repetitions (grey lines) of each application with a fixed number of processes. For phase identification, we considered the time window during which a phase showed the most occurrences, based on a specific metric (i.e., I/O hits). The red dashed lines indicate the average used as reference during model calibration.

Model Calibration Starting from the Markovian model introduced in Section 2, we set the color class *Application* to a single color, as we consider only one application per time step for calibration purposes. Using FTIO, we identify distinct alternating patterns of different types. Consequently, we need to calibrate the unknown transition parameters such that the model dynamics fit the reference data by minimizing the objective function defined in Eq. 1 in the main paper.

Thus, the transition rates- specifically, the exponential distributions governing each transition- are time-dependent, with each cluster of phases being characterized by its own distinct constant rate. Figure 3 shows the fitting results, illustrating a representative subset of our calibration outcomes. Although only a partial selection is displayed for simplicity, consistent results were obtained across all cases depicted in 2.

These measurements demonstrate that leveraging phase detection can effectively feed our machine model to generate synthetic performance data matching

real-world traces, as illustrated in Figure 3. Finally, we aim to validate the effectiveness of scheduling multiple applications to mitigate contention. We use our machine learning model, HPC-ESSN, to get hypotheses regarding contention by introducing phase shifts between applications that are likely to contend. The likelihood of contention is characterized by both the intensity of events (in our case, I/O operations) and the Lowest Common Multiplier of their periods, with lower LCM values indicating a higher frequency of interactions between programs. Next, we present a comparative analysis of the gains achievable through various phase shifts between applications.

3.1 Phase Shift and Simulation

The figure consists of two parts: the top part shows the data categorized by type of state (color-coded), while the bottom panel organizes the same information by application. The first column represents the best-case scenario, where ample resources are available. In contrast, the worst case (last column) shows a computation surge at time zero due to resource contention. The plots reveal the impact of staggering the start times of each application on system behavior and resource utilization. Notably, they show an increase in computations during specific time windows of the simulation, highlighting the benefits of carefully designed scheduling strategies in optimizing resource usage and minimizing delays.

Application	2 Servers scheduled starting time			
	scheduling 1	scheduling 2	scheduling 3	scheduling 4
1: Benchmark 2 proc	0.00	0.00	0.00	200.00
2: Benchmark 2 proc	500.00	80.00	1200.00	1200.00
3: Benchmark 4 proc	900.00	1000.00	900.00	900.00
4: Benchmark 4 proc	1300.00	1100.00	200.00	200.00
5: Benchmark 8 proc	1600.00	1600.00	200.00	200.00
6: Benchmark 16 proc	1900.00	1700.00	0.00	0.00
7: Benchmark 32 proc	2100.00	900.00	0.00	0.00
8: Epigraph 1 proc	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
9: Epigraph 2 proc	0.00	250.00	200.00	200.00
10: Epigraph 8 proc	1000.00	700.00	500.00	500.00
11: Epigraph 4 proc	1500.00	1800.00	1000.00	1000.00
12: Epigraph 16 proc	2000.00	2000.00	0.00	2000.00

Table 1: Summary of the starting time shifts for the four scheduled scenarios.

Table 1 provides an overview of the shifting in the starting time for each scheduled scenario considered in the analysis. Each row represents a scheduled scenario detailing the specific shifting made to the starting times of individual applications to minimize queuing. Scenarios representing the worst-case and

best-case situations, where all applications start simultaneously at time zero, were omitted for simplicity.

References

1. Marsan, M.A., Balbo, G., Conte, G., Donatelli, S., Franceschinis, G.: Modelling with Generalized Stochastic Petri Nets. J. Wiley, New York, NY, USA (1995)
2. Pernice, S., Follia, L., Balbo, G., Sartini, G., Totis, N., Lió, P., Merelli, I., Cordero, F., Beccuti, M.: Integrating petri nets and Flux balance methods in computational biology models: a methodological and computational practice. *Fundamenta Informaticae* **171**(1-4), 367–392 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3233/FI-2020-1888>
3. Pernice, S., Pennisi, M., Romano, G., Maglione, A., Cutrupi, S., Pappalardo, F., Balbo, G., Beccuti, M., Cordero, F., Calogero, R.A.: A computational approach based on the colored Petri Net formalism for studying multiple sclerosis. *BMC bioinformatics* **20**(6), 1–17 (2019)

Fig. 2: *Phase Detection* with FTIO for EpiGraph (top) and malleable benchmarks (bottom). The columns show the number of processes, and the rows represent the four metrics from the Metric Proxy. The colored areas indicate clustered phases. Additionally, the grey line shows the variability of the target metric, while the dashed red line marks its average.

Fig. 3: Model calibration results for EpiGraph and malleable benchmarks across different process counts. Red lines show actual metric traces, black lines the average of 100 stochastic simulations, and grey areas indicate the variation range.

Fig. 4: Average total number of I/O, MPI, and other computation calls across the simulation of the six scenarios.